

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TOHON****FIRST NAME: HERMANN****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 10%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Consider these research steps: (a) defining the question, (b) researching the topic, (c) organizing your ideas, and (d) writing the essay. What is the correct order of research steps?
 - d-a-c-b.
 - c-a-b-d.
 - b-a-c-d.¹**
 - a-b-c-d.
2. What is the correct answer?
 - The research question is only consistent with the title.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7-10.

- The research question is consistent with the research question and literature review elements.²**
- The research question is only consistent with literature review elements.
- The research question is inconsistent with the research question and the literature review.
3. What is the introduction and literature review different?
- Research question.
- Research Statement.
- Literature review.
- Operational definition of terms.³**
4. What is not a plagiarism?
- You do not plagiarize when you use the words of a source without quotation marks.
- You do not plagiarize when the information you write about is common knowledge.⁴**
- You do not plagiarize when you take ideas from a source without footnoting the source.
- You do not plagiarize when you use the data of a source without footnoting the source.
5. What is not the element of any argument?

² James Sampson P., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second ed. (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 29.

³ Ibid., 27-33.

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 37.

- Claim.
 - Evidence.
 - Significance.**⁵
 - Reason.
6. What is the main difference between the bibliography entries and reference list entries?
- Date (year) of publication.**⁶
 - Edition.
 - Capitalization.
 - Publisher's name.
7. Select the wrong answer, which is not a validity assessment.
- Construct Validity.
 - Factorial Validity.
 - Question validity.**⁷
 - Discriminant Validity.
8. Choose the correct answer for data validity.
- Congruence.**⁸
 - Criterion.
 - Goodness.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

⁶ Ibid., 169-242.

⁷ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 41.

⁸ Ibid., 47.

- Rightness.
9. What is not a stance to describe a philosophical paradigm of research design?
- Ontological stance.
- Epistemological stance.
- Axiological stance.
- Philosophical stance.**⁹
10. What is not a qualitative research design?
- Descriptive approach.**¹⁰
- Narrative approach.
- Case-study approach.
- Grounded theory approach.

⁹ Adu Philip, 'Conducting qualitative research: Writing the methodology chapter', NCADE, March 6, 2016, Video of lecture, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&t=19s>.

¹⁰ Ibid.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adu Philip, 'Conducting qualitative research: Writing the methodology chapter', NCADE, March 6, 2016, Video of lecture, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&t=19s>.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Sta. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.